

A spatial temporal analysis of acute encephalitis syndrome and Japanese encephalitis in Gaya district in Bihar

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Abstract

Acute Encephalitis Syndrome and Japanese Encephalitis is one of the major vector borne disease prevalent in the Asia. With approximately 68000 cases and 1320 deaths each year, the disease is more threat to the society. The risk population of this disease is basically aged below 15 year population. Thus, the objective of this paper is to understand the spatio-temporal prevalence of this disease in Gaya district which after 2009 has seen several outbreak. The methodology adopted to understand is mapping the disease cases at sub district level, block, in order to understand the region from which region contribute most of the reported cases of AES/JE from the district. The spatial region were further analyzed with the IDW methodology in order to locate the specific region which contributes most of the cases. The result shows that the entire block of the district has reported one or more cases over the year and the disease has spread to several new foci in the period between 2013-2020. The number of cases recorded has shown uneven trend as some year had contributed most of the cases while the interment year shows a rapid decrease in the number of cases. The IDW analysis also clearly represent that the foci of disease reporting has shown tremendous change over the year as the reporting region is shifting from norther part of the district towards the southern extremes.

Key Words: Spatio-Temporal, Aes/Je, Idw, Risk Population.

Introduction

Vector- borne disease is a illness caused by parasite, viruses and bacteria transferred to human by the vectors as mosquito, sandflies etc is one of the major infectious disease burdens in the world and poses a serious threat to the human society. The significant threat posed by vector-borne diseases can be understood from the fact that it constitutes 17% of the global burden of communicable diseases and claims more than 7 lakh lives every year, more than 80% of the world population is at risk of one major vector-borne disease, while 50% of the global population is at risk of two or more vector-borne diseases, especially the vulnerable section of the society (Global Vector Control Response, WHO 2017). With approximately 68000 cases and 1320 deaths each year, Japanese encephalitis (JE) is one of the most common vector-borne diseases globally. (Campbell et al., 2011). The disease is caused by a flavivirus spread by mosquitoes and is present in the south and east of Asia (there currently exist 24 nations with JE virus transmission). (Heffelfinger et al, 2017). The condition affects children under the age of 15 years (Umenai, 1985). Underreporting of cases results in conservative estimates of 50,000 cases annually, a death rate of 25–30%, and with long-term sequelae of 30–40% [WHO, 2008]. This number is thought to represent only a small percentage of the real burden of the disease. Infected animals, typically domestic pigs and migratory birds, transmit the virus to people through culicine mosquitoes (primarily *Culex vishnui* group).

According to Soman (1986), humans are not thought to be an reservoir for viral transmission. Japanese Encephalitis is one of the prevalent vector borne disease in Bihar. According to the NVBDCP out of the 60 high priority district of Japanese Encephalitis in India, Bihar have 9 district which fall under the high priority districts of AES/JE. The disease burden in the state ranges from 4.7 to 25.0 incidence rates per lakh population, and the trend is shown to increase since 2009 (Kumar et al., 2016).

The objective of this article is to understand the temporal pattern of the number of cases of AES / JE reported in the Gaya district and to understand the spatial distribution of these to formulate a clear understanding of the extent of risk through these diseases in the district. A spatial distribution of the recorded cases has been mapped in the district through Arc Map environment. The population at risk has been analyzed by dividing in the several age category in order to understand the risk population for this particular disease. The incidence rate is computed for the district average population 0-14 from census of India data.

Burden of AES/JE Cases in Gaya District.

The burden of AES / JE cases in Bihar reveals that 3206 total cases were registered between 2013 and 2020. The total number of AES/JE cases recorded from the Gaya district within the same time frame is 411, making up more than 12% of all cases in the state. The number of AES/JE cases reported from the district and the state exhibit an erratic pattern. In 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and

2019 the district experiences an AES/JE outbreak. While the intermittent years like 2013 and 2018 and 2020 indicate a lesser number of instances. As a result, the district's overall pattern is put at greater

danger due to the district's inconsistent pattern of AES/JE cases. Table 1: Number of cases of AES / JE reported in Gaya district and Bihar State.

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Gaya	23	72	74	101	55	8	71	7
Bihar	580	1341	298	324	189	124	292	58
Incidence Rate*	1.33	4.19	4.31	5.88	3.20	0.46	4.13	0.40

Source: State Health Malaria Office. * Calculated by author.

The fact that the majority of the population at risk of AES / JE are children under the age of 15 helps explain the burden of the disease. All AES/JE reporting cases had a median age of seven years or less. According to the Gaya district's population at risk, children between the ages of 2 and 10 are the groups most commonly impacted by these diseases. According to the data, cases in the 2 to 5 year old age group were on the decline until 2018, but then suddenly increased in 2019 and 2020. This suggests that this age group has the highest risk of

contracting these diseases. While over the same time period the number of cases reported for AES/JE in the age group of 5 to 10 years increased until 2018, when the number of reported cases in this category reached its highest level, it was then shown to be declining in 2019 and 2020. The reporting of AES/JE in the infant age group according to our result shows except in the year 2013 and 2014 the registered cases has suddenly dropped which shows that the control of these disease occurs in the age group is related with vaccination measures undertaken by the government.

Figure 1: The number of AES/JE reported from the different age category.

Source: Computed and Prepared by the author.

Spatial Distribution of AES/JE cases in Gaya District.

The spatial distribution of cases of AES / JE in the Gaya district from 2013 to 2020 shows an erratic pattern, so a proper analysis is carried out to understand the spatial distribution of AES/JE at the block level. The result shows that the distribution pattern of the AES/JE cases in the block follows an erratic pattern, but the most common block that continuously reports low cases to very high cases in the district, the Gaya CD Block, which records the highest cases in 2014 and 2019. The Bodh Gaya also continuously blocks the cases of AES/JE in all the respective years except in 2020. Except in 2018 and 2020 all blocks have registered AES / JE cases in

our study period. The pattern of cases of AES/JE is concentrated around these two blocks and its adjoining block. The other interesting feature noticed through this analysis is that almost all blocks have become the centre of one or more cases in the respective years, thus showing that the distribution of these diseases in new foci. This analysis provides us with a clear understanding of the spatial distribution of these cases in the district. As these block which registers from no cases to low-high cases shows that entire region of the district is at risk of recording of the cases of these disease.

The incidence rate mapping provide us a clear picture of continuous surface and the occurrence of AES/JE Cases in Gaya district. It provides us bull eye possibility of the occurrence of

these diseases in the district. The result from the IDW analysis clearly shows that there is a shift of the incidence rate from the northern part of the district to the southern region, thus providing us a understanding that the cases has been reported from the foci over the years. This analysis also provides

us a understanding the concentration of reported cases. The major concentration of high and very high cases are located mostly in the Gaya CD Block and Bodh Gaya Block thus confirming with the spatial distribution of cases as observed above.

Source: Prepared by the author.

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Conclusions

The AES/JE caused by the Culex mosquito in the risk population especially in children is one of the most prevalent vector-borne diseases in Bihar. The analysis shows that the age category of the reporting

cases of AES/JE is highest in the group of children of 2 to 10 years of age. The temporal pattern of registered cases in the district also shows that the number of cases varies widely yearly. The highest reporting cases above from a single district are found in the year 2014 to 2017 and again a peak is

observed in 2019. Although the interment year 2013, 2018 and 2020 show a rapid decrease in the cases. This erratic pattern of reporting of cases gives us insight that the disease spread and its spatial distribution need to be understood, which led to our second analysis in which we had looked at the spatial distribution of the cases at the block level. The block level spatial distribution analysis shows us that the block surrounding Gaya CD Block and Bodh Gaya Block in the central part shows a larger number of the reported cases of AES/JE in our study period. The spatio-temporal distribution has been conceptualized by the Inverse distance weighting (IDW) methodology. The pattern clearly shows a shift of the incidence cases of AES/JE from northern part of the district towards the southern part showing that the geographical expansion of the disease over the period of time.

Limitation of the study

The causal factor for this disease has not been considered in our present paper as it tries to understand the spatial distribution of these reported of disease, which is a first step in order to conduct further study.

References

1. Campbell GL, Hills SL, Fischer M, Jacobson JA, Hoke CH, Hombach JM, et al (2011). Estimated global incidence of Japanese encephalitis: a systematic review. *Bull World Health Organ.* 89(10):766-74, 774 A - 774 E.
2. Heffelfinger JD, Li X, Batmunkh N, Grabovac V, Diorditsa S, Liyanage, JB, et al (2017). Japanese Encephalitis Surveillance and Immunisation - Asia and Western Pacific Regions, 2016. *Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 66(22); 579-83.
3. http://www.who.int/immunization_delivery/new_vaccines/je/en/ 20 April 2008.
4. Kumar P, Pisudde PM, Sarthi PP, Sharma MP, Keshri (2016). Acute encephalitis syndrome and Japanese encephalitis, status, and trends in Bihar State, India. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases, Poster Presentation, Volume 45, Supplement 1, 306-307.*
5. Soman RS, Mourya DT, Mishra AC (1986). Transovarial transmission of the Japanese encephalitis virus in *Culex vishnui* mosquitoes. *Ind J Med Res;* 84: 283-85.
6. Umenai TR, Krzysko TA, Bektimirov, Assaad FA (1985). Japanese encephalitis: Current Worldwide Status. *Bull WHO;* 63: 625-31.
7. WHO (2008). Japanese encephalitis (JE). Delivery of the vaccination service and rapid disease control. Programmes and projects.
8. WHO (2017). Global Vector Control Response 2017-2030. Online access. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512978>.